

UAV PHOTOGRAMMETRY-BASED MAPPING OF SICILIAN POCKET BEACHES: FIRST APPROACH

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ABSTRACT:

The Pocket Beaches (PBs) are widespread throughout the Mediterranean coast and the characteristics of their landscape make them very attractive for tourists. Along the Sicilian coast there are several Pocket Beaches. However, they have no univocal behaviour. Numerous detailed studies on Pocket Beaches have been carried out in recent years; they suggested that geometric physical parameters provide useful information for characterization of embayed coasts. These parameters allow for the analysis of coastal segments exposure to the incident waves and are usually extracted from old dataset or from hazardous fieldworks. In this study, we propose a UAV- photogrammetry-based mapping approach to study the PBs located on the coast of Sicily. With the aid of new technologies, we used drones equipped with very high-resolution camera to acquired orthophotos and 3-D representation of Sicilian PBs. The data obtained by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles were supported by Ground control Points acquired using RTK GPS which helped refine their geo-referencing precision. Computer-assisted approach was adopted to retrieve geometric parameters and eventually coastal geomorphological elements of the PBs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pocket Beaches (PBs), are small beaches, included between two headlands (natural or artificial promontories). These headlands play an important role in the beach natural functioning, they constitute either the morphological definition of the beach system, or the structure dominating the local wave conditions.. The PBs are widespread throughout the Mediterranean coast (Bowman, 2009) and the characteristics of their exceptional natural landscape make them very attractive for tourists. Along the Sicilian coast (main island of Sicily and related archipelagos), there are several Pocket Beaches. These ones are quite varied and present a strong differentiation linked to their geodiversity. Numerous detailed studies on Pocket Beaches have been carried out in recent years (Pranzini, 2013; Klein, 2002; Bowman, 2009); they suggested that geometric physical parameters provide useful information for characterization of embayed coasts (Bowman, 2014).

These parameters allow to monitor coastal segments exposure to 1) the incident waves, 2) the response of the beaches to the big storms, 3) coastal and beach erosion and 4) nearshore morphological changes. However, these parameters are usually extracted from old dataset or from hazardous fieldworks (Bowman, 2009). Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) are photogrammetric platforms that operate autonomously, semi-autonomously or through a remote control and allow the acquisition of very high spatial resolution imageries. In addition, their ability of operating in hard-to-reach areas made UAV- photogrammetry, the cost-effective environmental survey technique. In this way, we propose a UAV- photogrammetry-based mapping approach to study the PBs located on the coast of Sicily.

We used drones equipped with very high-resolution camera to acquire orthophotos and 3-D representation of Sicilian PBs. The data obtained by UAVs has been supported by Ground Control

Points (GCPs) acquired using RTK GPS which helped to refine their geo-referencing precision. Computer-assisted approach was adopted to retrieve information on geometric parameters and eventually coastal geomorphological elements of the PBs. This study is the first geomorphological approach, conducted in the framework of the BESS project - Pocket Beach Management and Remote Surveillance System Project (BESS) (Figure 1), following other propaedeutic scientific contributions focused about: 1) the use of multispectral satellite image to explore shallow water bathymetry (Randazzo et al., 2020 and Muzirafuti et al., 2020), 2) the interaction between *Posidonia o.* and PBs evolution (Tomasello et al., 2020) and 3) the implementation of WebGIS Implementation for Dynamic Mapping Visualization (Randazzo et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Map showing the locations of 117 pocket beaches (PBs) belonging the 8 coastal provinces of Agrigento, Caltanissetta, Catania, Messina, Palermo, Ragusa, Siracusa and

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Trapani. In the BESS project 132 were studied, including the 15 placed between Malta and Gozo.

In the BESS project all Sicilian and Maltese PBs have been studied. The paper aims at presenting a methodological approach actually applied on Sicilian PBs, but which could be adopted for a regular monitoring of the whole Sicilian coastal area (Randazzo & Lanza, 2020).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Data acquisition

Two major campaigns were carried out during the acquisition of the data analysed by BESS project. The first survey has been conducted in the spring/summer season of 2019. Due to the restrictions related to the Covid-19, the second survey has been carried out in the autumn/winter season of 2019/2020 and in the autumn winter season of 2020/2021. The surveys involved all the Sicilian and Maltese Pocket Beaches, except for the PBs located in areas close to airports where high spatial resolution satellite images (WorldView-2/3) (Ye, 2017) were used.

The surveys were carried out using different UAVs such as DJI Mavic 2 Pro, Matrices 210 RTK and the Matrice 600 Pro equipped with optical sensors (Figure 2a). To acquire images, the surveys were carried out from an acquisition altitude of about 65 m with camera at Nadir angle view. Image frames were taken, with an overlap between successive frames equal to 75% on the horizontal and 75% on the vertical. To improve the positioning accuracy of images, for each survey, GCPs were acquired and used for georeferencing purpose.

GCPs coordinates were acquired using the Topcon Hyper HR Base Rover satellite acquisition system. This system is composed of a BASE and ROVER differential GPS in RTK (Real Time Kinematic) mode (Figure 2b). The reference system used for the acquisition of the GCPs was the WGS84 UTM 33 N (EPSG 32633). During GCPs acquisition, localization accuracy per GCP was set to 0.02 m. In addition, measures were taken, to reduce the mean errors in the three coordinate directions, by recording the value provided by high number satellites.

Figure 2. Example of AUV used for acquisition of the data Matrice 600 (a) and the Topcon Hyper HR Base-Rover satellite acquisition system used for GCPs data acquisition (B).

In average, 39 hours 29 minutes and 11 seconds were used during the second photogrammetry survey for 109 PBs located on 7 provinces of Sicily. With the longest flight lasting 2h 6 min 53 sec while the shortest flight lasted 5 min 3 sec.

2.2 Dataset creation

Images acquired during the surveys were processed using the Pix4D Mapper software. This software allows to integrate aerial images and CGPs to generate very high spatial resolution georeferenced orthophotos, Digital Surface Model (DSM) and Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The process involves five

steps including a) importing the images; b) identification of clearly recognizable points in the various frames; c) correlation between homologous points during the matching phase; d) bundle-adjustment processing; and after inserting the GCPs, e) the generation of very high-resolution spatial (up to 1.5 cm) georeferenced orthophotos and DSM (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of orthophoto and Digital Surface Model (DSM) obtained from the survey conducted on the PB of Noto-Fondo Morte (Siracusa) within the project with the label SIC76SR09.

In total, 1258 GCPs were acquired for accessible 90 PBs located on the coast of seven provinces of Sicily. For Messina province 258 GCPs were used acquired, the highest number of GCPs was acquired on the coast of Siracusa (318 GCPs) while the small number was acquired on 2 PBs of Catania (22 GCPs). For the provinces of Agrigento, Palermo, Ragusa and Trapani, 48, 122, 268 and 222 GCPs were acquired respectively.

Integration of GCPs in images processing plays an important role for dataset georeferencing evaluation. They allow to evaluate the absolute position uncertainty, which is in our case up to 4 cm of precision, and eventually georeferencing precision accuracy of the dataset where the average range of mean RMS error is estimated at 0.01 to 0.1 m.

2.3 Data processing

While UAV- photogrammetry technique was used to acquire very high-resolution spatial (up to 1.5 cm) georeferenced orthophotos and DEM, computer-assisted approach was adopted for their analysis. It is important to note that very high-resolution spatial orthophotos and DEM consume a lot of processing power. In this way, we use high performing hardware and sophisticated software to retrieve information on geometric parameters and eventually coastal geomorphological elements of the PBs. We used 3 desktop computers with Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-1620 v4, 3.50 GHz processor and 32,0 GB of Random-Access Memory (RAM) and ArcGIS 10.2 software to process the data. The following geometric parameters (Bowman, 2014) were extracted from the dataset:

Ro is the rope between the two headlands, defining the PB [m];

S1 is the length of the embedding [m]

S2 is the length of the beach itself [m];

S3 is the linear distance of the segment stretched between the limits of the beach [m];

S2p represents the maximum beach width;

Sp beach surface [m²];

a represents the indentation, so the perpendicular distance [m] between the midpoint of **Ro** and **S1**;

am represents the distance between the midpoint of **Ro** and the widest sector of the beach.

To guarantee the precision of retrieve information, manual digitization approach has been adopted and used. Retrieved

information were represented on maps (Figure 4). These are parameters which are mainly involved in the computation of indentation index, embaymentization index and the bay filling index (Bowman, 2014). They are crucial for classification and characterisation of PBs, but we also considered 1) the closure depth in terms of position: if external, internal or on the rope, 2) the geological characteristics of the headlands and 3) the dominating wind.

Figure 4. Plainview of the geometric parameters obtained from orthophoto of the survey conducted on a PB (in this case Noto-Fondo Morte Siracusa individuated).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For the 117 PBs located on the coast of Sicily, we present the statistical summary including the range of geometric parameters and their corresponding number of PBs. While 2 campaigns were conducted during the BESS project, here the results of analysis of the second survey are presented. The results show that:

- **Ro** has an average high values varying between 2188 and 504 m representing 21 PBs; the average mean values vary between 497 and 200 m representing 50 PBs, the average low values vary between 196 and 27 m, representing 33 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 4349 and 19 m for the PB of Modica-Maganuco and the PB of Santa Flavia Porto di Spagna respectively.
- **(S1)** has an average high values varying between 3287 and 977 m representing 26 PBs, the average mean values vary between 970 and 366 m representing 57 PBs, the average low values vary between 360 and 113 m representing 30 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 5548 and 99 m for the PB of Modica-Maganuco and the PB of Custunaci Agliareddi respectively.
- **(S2)** has an average high values varying between 1598 and 307 m representing 35 PBs, the average mean values vary between 297 and 121 m representing 43 PBs, the average low values vary between 119 and 35 m representing 35 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 1,919 and 11 m for the PB of Scicli-Sampieri Fornace Penna and the PB of Mazara-Torretta Granitola (North) respectively. **(S2p)** is not significative at this point.
- **(S3)** has an average high values varying between 1379 and 402 m representing 24 PBs, the average mean values vary

between 309 and 109 m representing 59 PBs, the average low values vary between 107 and 20 m representing 30 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 1770 and 11 m for the PB of Scicli-Sampieri Fornace Penna and the PB of Mazara-Torretta Granitola (North) respectively.

- **(Sp)** has an average high values vary between 70,002 and 10,179 m² representing 31 PBs, the average mean values vary between 9,809 and 1,006 m² representing 62 PBs, the average low values vary between 840 and 58 m² representing 20 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 78061 and 33 m² for the PB of Scicli-Sampieri Fornace Penna and the PB of Mazara-Torretta Granitola (North) respectively.
- **(a)** has an average high value varying between 720 and 304 m representing 16 PBs, the average mean values vary between 286 and 86 m representing 67 PBs, the average low values vary between 82 and 21 m representing 31 PBs; while the highest and lowest values are 788 and 16 m for the PB of Siracusa-Fontane Bianche (North) and the PB of Panarea Preistorico respectively. **(am)** follows the same pattern.

These values, taken together, do not give us the possibility of arriving at a clear explanation. For this reason, we have selected the most identifying ones, from the geomorphological point of view, like the rope and the arrow and we have observed them, according to their different geological context.

In fact, it is important to underline that Sicily represents an extraordinary index of differentiation from the geological point of view (GEODIVERSITY) which is reflected into the coastal features (Lanza & Randazzo, 2011; 2013). In this paper we try to relate the shape of the PBs in function of the prevalent lithologies outcropping around them. Trying to simplify, we identified: 1) igneous rocks belonging the Etna Volcano (Catania) and the Aeolian Islands, 2) metamorphic rocks present in the western province of Messina, 3) flysch and clayey series outcropping in the eastern province of Messina, east of Palermo and in an area between Trapani and Agrigento, 4) hard limestones into both the Iblean Plateau (Siracusa and Ragusa) and the Mountains of Trapani (including part of the territory of Palermo), 5) soft limestones (prevalently marles) of the provinces of Agrigento, and finally 6) the sedimentary deposits of the Caltanissetta coastline.

To further have another two control keys we introduce the wind dominance in five different sectors around the island coastline and finally we consider the position of the closure depth of each single Pocket Beach.

The relationship between headland spacing (**Ro**) and bay indentation (**a**) has been evaluated for the PBs located in different geological settings (Figure 5).

For each group of PBs the location of the Closure depth (Cd) has been determined: 1) inshore from both headlands, 2) offshore from one headland and 3) offshore from both headlands.

Its locations allow to classify the PBs in three categories:

- Closed: for the Cd located inshore from both headlands
- Semi-closed: for the Cd located offshore from one headland
- Open: for the Cd located offshore from both headlands.

The results reveal that, many PBs located in hard limestones settings are open with headland spacing varies between 50 and 550 m. For those located in soft limestones, this number increases with a mix of open and semi-closed PBs. Many mixed closed and semi-closed PBs is in igneous rocks. Sedimentary deposits, metamorphic rocks, flysch and clayey series each hold a small number of semi-closed and closed PBs (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Evaluation of embayment of the PBs located in different geological settings based on headland spacing (R_o) and bay indentation (a).

The results indicate that the proposed methodology provide updated and precise information on the shape and the size of the PBs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, UAV- photogrammetry-based mapping technique is used to acquire very high-spatial resolution imageries of the PBs located on the coast of Sicily. The UAV- photogrammetry-based mapping allows for the creation of very detailed and updated high resolution imageries adapted for small changes evolution analysis. The acquired imageries are analysed using computer-assisted approach which allows for extraction of very precise extraction of geomorphological parameters information. The proposed methodology can be used for regular monitoring of standard beach areas.

For the future study, information obtained, in this study, will be involved in the computation of indentation index, embaymentization index and the bay filling index needed for the classification and characterisation of PBs of Sicily.

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